

Substances related to Cochinillic and Carminic Acids.

Part II. A Synthesis of α -Coccinic Acid

(*m*-Oxyuvitic Acid).

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It was found by the authors (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 201; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 4) and also by Schleussner and Voswinkel (*Annalen*, 1921, 422, 111) that the condensation of chloral with *m*-cresotic acid produces a complex mixture of substances. The authors, because it appeared to them that this complexity depended largely on the activity of the hydroxyl group in the *m*-cresotic acid, decided to study the condensation of chloral with the methyl ether of this acid, that is, with 2-methoxy-*p*-toluic acid. The main product of this condensation was found to be 2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloro-ethylbenzene I. This on reduction gave 2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1- $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl benzene, II (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*).

This condensation has now been more fully investigated. It is found that there are produced, in addition to I, the substance III (2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethyl benzene) and a sulphonic acid, which is IV (2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-3-sulpho-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl benzene).

Chattaway and Calvet (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 133, 2914) have obtained from chloral and *p*-nitroanisole, as the sole product of the reaction, a substance that contains the same group, $-\text{CHCl}.\text{CCl}_3$, as is present in III. The authors find that the substance III is produced, in small amount, along with I. It can be obtained from I (a) by dissolving in sulphuric acid and passing in hydrochloric acid gas; (b) on heating I with sulphuric acid on the water-bath for about 10 minutes. Each substance, I and III, can be reduced to the same substance II. Under treatment with potassium hydroxide solution the substance III yields the trichlorostyrene V.

The substance I, on hydrolysis of the $-\text{CCl}_3$ group, yields the mandelic acid VI, which gives (i) on oxidation, the phenyl-glyoxylic acid VII, and (ii) on treatment with sulphuric acid, with loss of carbon monoxide, the aldehyde VIII. This aldehyde, on oxidation, gives the methyl ether of α -coccinic acid IX, and this, on hydrolysis, gives α -coccinic acid, X.

Oppenheim and Pfaff prepared α -coccinic acid (*m*-oxyuvitic acid) from ethyl acetoacetate and chloroform (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 929). The

same acid was subsequently obtained by Liebermann and Voswinc²¹ as a degradation product of cochinnilic acid and was named α -coccinic acid (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1733). The melting point of this substance was doubtful: Beilstein says 295-298° (*Handbuch der Org. Chemie*, 1927, 10, 512); Claisen observed 310° as the temperature of decomposition (*Annalen*, 1897, 237, 44). The authors found that α -coccinic acid, obtained as described in this paper, and by the method of Oppenheim and Pfaff, melted at 320-322° with decomposition. The specimen, obtained by the latter method, was methylated and was found to be identical with the methyl ether of α -coccinic acid already prepared.

The substance II on treatment with sulphuric acid undergoes a change in which the group $-\text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CHCl}_2$, by hydrolysis and oxidation, becomes $\text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2\text{H}$. This remarkable change was first observed by Meldrum and Vaidyanathan in work not yet published: it affords a valuable means of producing substituted phenylacetic acids, *e.g.*; XI.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1-*a*-hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl benzene (I), 2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethyl benzene (III) and 2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-3-sulpho-1-*a*-hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl benzene (IV).

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1-*a*-hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl benzene has been already described (*J. Indian Chem. Soc., loc. cit.*). The authors have now been able to obtain this compound in larger yield (52 per cent.) along with the substances III and IV.

2-Methoxy-*p*-toluic acid (20 g.), chloral hydrate (24 g.) and sulphuric acid (96.97 per cent., 40 c.c.) were mixed. After 7 days the mixture was poured into water containing ice when a white solid separated (30 g.). The mother-liquor (A) was worked up separately (see below). A solution of this solid in glacial acetic acid gave about 20 grams of I and the mother-liquor gave substance III (1.5 g.) which crystallised from alcohol in rectangular plates, m. p. 200-201°. (Found: Cl, 42.57. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 42.73 per cent.)

The substance III was obtained more quickly in two ways: (a) The trichloromethyl carbinol I (1 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) and the solution was saturated with hydrogen chloride and left for a day at ordinary temperature; (b) the trichloromethyl carbinol I (4 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (40 c.c.) and the solution was heated on the water-bath for 10 minutes. In each case the solution was poured into water and the solid that separated was crystallised from alcohol. [Yield (a) 0.3 g., m. p. 200-201°; (b) yield 2.4 g., m. p. 200-201°.] The substance III on reduction with zinc dust and acetic acid yielded II.

Formation of $\alpha\beta\beta$ -Trichloro-2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxystyrene (V).—The tetrachloro compound (1 g.) was heated for about 15 minutes with potassium hydroxide solution (20 per cent., 25 c.c.). After cooling, the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in plates, m. p. 185-187°. (Found: Cl, 36.21; equivalent, 295.1. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 36.06 per cent.; equivalent, 295.4.)

The sulphuric acid mother-liquor (A) was neutralised with $BaCO_3$. The clear solution was evaporated on the water-bath when a precipitate was formed which was found to be a mixture of $BaSO_4$ and the barium salt of the condensation product I. The mixture was filtered and the clear solution was kept in an evacuated desiccator over

H_2SO_4 . The *barium* salt of IV crystallises in silky needles. (Found: Ba, 25.74. $C_{11}H_9O_7Cl_3S$ Ba requires Ba, 25.98 per cent.)

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxymandelic acid (VI).—The trichloromethyl carbinol I (10 g.) was boiled for an hour with a solution of barium hydroxide (50 g.) in water (200 c.c.). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate on cooling yielded the barium salt of the mandelic acid (VI). The filtrate on evaporation gave a further yield of the *barium* salt in tiny needles. (Found: Ba, 30.7. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6Ba, 4H_2O$ requires Ba, 30.7 per cent.) The salt was acidified with hydrochloric acid until a clear solution was obtained. Barium was removed as $BaSO_4$ and the filtrate was evaporated to small bulk. The hydroxy acid crystallises very slowly and even after seeding takes generally more than 12 hours to get the maximum yield of 6 grams. Recrystallised from ethyl acetate, in tiny groups of needles, it sinters at 95-100° and melts at 105-110° with effervescence. The crystals contain 1 molecule of water. When the substance is dried at 70-80° it melts at 162-163°. (The hydrated substance, found: equivalent, 129.2; H_2O , 7.3. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6, H_2O$ requires equivalent, 129.05; H_2O , 7 per cent. The anhydrous substance, found: equivalent, 120.3. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires 120.05.)

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxyphenylglyoxylic acid (VII).—The hydroxy acid just described (1 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution: potassium permanganate (1 g.) dissolved in water (40 c.c.) was added. Oxidation takes place easily and is over in about half an hour. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was reduced to a small bulk and then acidified. The substance was recrystallised from hot water in needles, m. p. 211-212°. (Found: equivalent, 119.4. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6$ requires 119.06.) The *barium* salt (microcrystalline) is very sparingly soluble in water. (Found: Ba, 33.68. $C_{11}H_8O_6Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 33.57 per cent.)

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (VIII).—The hydroxy acid (1.5 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (97 per cent., 4 c.c.) at 80-100°. Carbon monoxide was evolved during about 15 minutes. The solution was then poured into water (25 c.c.). The aldehyde separated in needles: it was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from water for analysis: m. p. 176-177°. (Found: equivalent, 193.8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ requires 194.04.)

α-Coccinic acid methyl ether (IX).—The aldehyde just described (1 g.) was dissolved in just sufficient potassium hydroxide solution: potassium permanganate (0.5 g.), dissolved in water (25 c.c.), was

added. Oxidation proceeded rapidly and was complete in about half an hour. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was reduced to small bulk and then acidified. The acid was crystallised from acetic acid and then from methyl alcohol in tiny groups of needles, m. p. 250-252°. (Found: equivalent, 105.3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires 105.04.)

The methyl ether of α -coccinic acid was also obtained by oxidation of the trichloromethyl carbinol I. The latter (1 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution: potassium permanganate (1 g.) dissolved in water (100 c.c.) was added and the mixture was heated on the water-bath for an hour. After removal of manganese oxide, the solution was reduced to small bulk and then acidified. The product was found to be identical with the α -coccinic acid methylether already obtained. (Found: equivalent, 104.5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires 105.04.)

α -Coccinic acid (X).—The methylether of α -coccinic acid (0.5 g.) was heated with hydriodic acid (10 per cent., 25 c.c.) under reflux for an hour. On cooling α -coccinic acid separated: it crystallised from acetic acid in shining plates: m. p. 320-322° with decomposition. For verification, the barium salt was prepared, purified and analysed (see below). The acid liberated from this salt was recrystallised from alcohol: m. p. 320-322° with decomposition. (Found: equivalent, 98.2. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires 98.03). The *calcium* salt (needles) crystallises with 4 molecules of water, of which $2\frac{1}{2}$ molecules can be removed at 110-115°. (Found: Ca, 13.2. $C_9H_8O_5Ca, 4H_2O$ requires 13.1 per cent.) After heating at 110-115° to constant weight, Ca, 15.51. $C_9H_8O_5Ca, 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires 15.35 per cent.) The *barium* salt (prismatic needles) crystallises with 2 molecules of water, of which $\frac{1}{2}$ molecule can be removed at 110-125°. (Found: Ba, 37.7. $C_9H_8O_5Ba, 2H_2O$ requires 37.4 per cent.) After heating at 110-115° to constant weight, found: Ba, 38.08. $C_9H_8O_5Ba, 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires 38.83 per cent.)

α -Coccinic acid was reported to melt at a temperature as low as 298° and as high as 310°. The acid was therefore prepared according to the method of Oppenheim and Pfaff from ethyl acetoacetate and chloroform in presence of sodium ethylate. α -Coccinic acid obtained in this way was impure. It was, therefore, converted into the barium salt, and a solution of this salt, after treatment with animal charcoal was acidified. The resulting solid having been found to be identical (m. p. 320-22° with decomposition) with the α -coccinic acid already prepared was methylated. The methylated product

melted at 250-52° and was identical with the methyl ether of *o*-cocci-
nic acid already obtained.

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-phenylacetic acid (XI).—*2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1-ββ-dichloroethylbenzene* II (1 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) at 70-80° for about an hour: HCl was evolved during the course of the reaction. The mixture was then poured into water (25 c.c.) when some unchanged substance separated which was removed. The filtrate on standing for about 2 days gave crystals (leaflets) which, on recrystallising from water, melted at 164-65°. (Found: equivalent, 112·7. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires 112·05.)

The *barium* salt (white leaflets) crystallises with $1\frac{1}{2}$ molecules of water. (Found: Ba, 35·6. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5Ba$, $1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires 35·56 per cent.)

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